

Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature – The Analysis Categories and Results

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Abstract. This paper presents the Analysis Categories and Results from the Journal Paper "Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature" published in the *Virtual Reality (VR) Journal*. This article analyses the state-of-the-art of virtual reality (VR) in higher education and provides an overview of the VR literature and identifies the need for the definition of key terms. Thus, it introduces three types of VR according to immersion level. Furthermore, analysis reveals a lack of systematic literature reviews (SLRs) on learning using immersive virtual reality (IVR). This article presents the results of the first SLR of the scientific literature on IVR in higher education indexed in Web of Science. A total of 291 articles were collected out of which 50 were selected for full-text analysis. We report three findings.

First, we categorise and cluster the literature into formal aspects and research design and conclude that IVR research remains in its infancy. Furthermore, it lacks a sound and standardised research framework and design as well as comparative studies that are repeated for validation.

Second, we analyse and discuss the current results and outcomes of the scientific research and identify the diversity of the reported research and learning outcomes with contradictory results, which are frequently due to specific and isolated scenarios.

Third, this work is the first systematic scoping review on all studies from Web of Science that focuses on the use of IVR in higher education in general. We offer a unique overview of scientific articles on IVR in higher education without any limitation in time, scope or topic. Notably, the majority of the 50 articles do not present evidence-based and validated results; in particular, discussions and results related to pedagogical aspects are lacking.

Keywords: Immersive virtual reality, Immersive learning and higher education, Systematic literature review, Web of Science database, PRISMA statement, Teachers and students, Pedagogical designs and Learning outcomes.

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1. Introduction and Background

For the Introduction and Background see Journal Paper "Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature" published in the *Virtual Reality (VR) Journal* (Stracke et al., 2025).

2. Levels of Immersion in VR and Learning Design for IVR

Basis is our definition of the following three key terms:

Non-immersive VR refers to VR experiences in which users view virtual content on a conventional display, remaining users aware of a visible boundary and frame between the virtual and the real world. Interactions indirectly occur via classical devices such as a mouse, keyboard or joystick. Note that this class is not truly VR, however, the term VR is often used to reflect this setting and thus is often misleading.

Semi-immersive VR still frames the virtual environment but uses large-scale projection surfaces, making visible boundaries and frames less apparent to users. Additionally, interactions occur via freehand gestures or tangible interfaces.

Immersive VR eliminates visible boundaries and frames allowing users to be fully enveloped in the virtual environment. Cave automatic virtual environments (CAVEs) employ a multi-projector configuration that envelops the user. These systems continue to be utilized in professional settings. Currently, HMDs are more frequently used and are affordable for private use. In immersive VR, visualisation continuously adapts to the head movements, including head rotation and translation. Input is performed via freehand gestures or special 3D interfaces such as controllers or haptic gloves.

Fig. 1. Three types of virtual reality

For the Levels of Immersion in VR and Learning Design for IVR see Journal Paper "Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature" published in the *Virtual Reality (VR) Journal* (Stracke et al., 2025).

3. Methodology

For the Methodology see Journal Paper "Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature" published in the *Virtual Reality (VR) Journal* (Stracke et al., 2025).

4. Results

We present the results of the SLR beginning with the results from the standardised and pre-defined selection process. We analyse specific aspects of the selected articles and outline the results, especially characteristics that can be described by objective values.

During the selection process, we identified 50 articles out of 291 initial records that met the inclusion criteria.

In total, we selected 50 articles according to their *in-depth analysis* (Section 4) and *subsequent discussion* (Section 5). All articles were compared and analysed according to our following analysis categories that we have developed in consensus before.

Table 1. Analysis categories for the selected articles.

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|-------------------------------------|----------------------|
| 1. Topic | 12. Study Validity |
| 2. Research Discipline | 13. Use Scenarios |
| 3. Research Country | 14. Target Group |
| 4. Authors' Discipline | 15. Media Mix |
| 5. Authors' Country | 16. Immersion |
| 6. Article Type | 17. Collaboration |
| 7. Number of Studies in the Article | 18. Interaction |
| 8. Study Type | 19. Learning Results |
| 9. Study Design (Evaluation Focus) | 20. Research Results |
| 10. Study Instruments | 21. Trust |
| 11. Study Formal Reporting | |

This paper "Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature – The Analysis Categories and Results" provides the full overview and key results of the analysis and is published as Annex to Stracke et al. (2025).

The full overview and key results of the analysis from the study “Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature – The Analysis Categories and Results” is provides in the following:

To be added after publication of the journal paper (Stracke et al., 2025).

References

- Stracke, C. M., Bothe, P., Adler, S., Heller, E. S., Deuchler, J., Pomino, J., & Wölfel, M. (2024). Immersive Virtual Reality in Higher Education: A Systematic Review of the Scientific Literature. *Virtual Reality*. (accepted, in publication)